

Effect of Microenvironmental Conditions on the Glycosaminoglycan Synthesis Rates of Nucleus Pulposus Cells

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INTRODUCTION:

Owing to its avascular nature, the intervertebral disc (IVD) has a unique microenvironment that varies with levels of degeneration. This microenvironment plays a key role in the function and survival of the intradiscal cells and therefore has a significant impact on the potential of regenerative therapies. Characterization of this microenvironment has been conducted through various studies [1, 2] but a lack of focus on the impact of the specific microenvironment on the cellular response is prominent throughout the literature. The aim of this work is to elucidate the effect of the IVD microenvironment on the matrix synthesis rates of nucleus pulposus cells, and ultimately to tailor cell therapies to optimize clinical outcomes. The microenvironment of the human IVD will be profiled assessing oxygen, glucose, pH and osmolarity levels as well as quantities of both regenerative and inflammatory cytokines and defined in vitro to analyze the cellular response and matrix production rates. To date the microenvironment of the IVD has been characterized as 2-10% oxygen [1], 1-5 mM glucose [3], 6.8-7.2 pH [1], 300-500 mOsm osmolarity [4] as well as a range of cytokines as outlined in figure 1a). Preliminary data has shown osmolarity, pH and glucose to have a notable effect on the matrix production rates of NP cells. (Figure 1 c)

METHODS:

Expanded goat NP cells were encapsulated in 1.5% alginate (Pronova UP LVG, FMC NovaMatrix, Norway) using a 20G needle, and ionically crosslinked with 100 mM calcium chloride for 20 minutes to form spherical beads at a seeding density of 2.5×10^6 cells/ml. Beads were cultured at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂ and 5% O₂ in phenol red and buffer free DMEM without glucose (Sigma-Aldrich 5030). Glucose was adjusted to 1mM and 3 mM, pH was adjusted to 6.8 and 7.1 and osmolarity was adjusted to 300 mOsm and 500 mOsm. Beads were cultured in 24 well plates with 2.5 ml of media per well, changed every 3 days to maintain the microenvironment conditions, as determined through in silico modelling (figure 1b). The beads were analyzed after 10 days in culture for cell viability, DNA and GAG content, and histologically stained.

RESULTS:

Figure 1 c) outlines the results of varying osmolarity, pH and glucose conditions. The GAG/DNA is altered by the selected microenvironmental conditions in all cases. Osmolarity and glucose variations result in a more prominent change in the GAG production rate than that observed with pH variations, with a 2.2, 2.4 and 1.6 fold increase observed respectively. Across all groups, values indicative of those found in healthy NP tissue resulted in an increased GAG production rate.

DISCUSSION:

Preliminary data demonstrated that microenvironmental conditions in line with those observed in healthy NP tissue resulted in increased GAG synthesis rates, similar to GAG quantities reported in previous studies [5]. All conditions demonstrated a notable effect on the matrix synthesis rates and future analysis will analyze the coupled effect of these conditions. This study has shown the microenvironmental profile of the IVD plays a vital role in the cellular response and is essential to the successful development of intradiscal therapies.

SIGNIFICANCE:

The microenvironment of the IVD plays a key role in the function and survival of the NP cells. This microenvironment is patient specific and varies greatly with levels of degeneration, undoubtedly impacting clinical outcomes for cell-based therapies. Analyzing the effect of the range of microenvironments on the matrix synthesis rates of NP cells will help tailor the future development of cell therapies to optimize clinical outcomes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

This work was supported by the European Research Council (ERC-2019-CoG-864104; INTEGRATE).

REFERENCES:

1. Bartels, E.M., et al., *Oxygen and lactate concentrations measured in vivo in the intervertebral discs of patients with scoliosis and back pain*. Spine (Phila Pa 1976), 1998. **23**(1): p. 1-7; discussion 8.
2. Bibby, S.R. and J.P. Urban, *Effect of nutrient deprivation on the viability of intervertebral disc cells*. Eur Spine J, 2004. **13**(8): p. 695-701.
3. Jackson, A.R., et al., *3D Finite Element Analysis of Nutrient Distributions and Cell Viability in the Intervertebral Disc: Effects of Deformation and Degeneration*. Journal of Biomechanical Engineering, 2011. **133**(9).
4. Sadowska, A., et al., *Osmosensing, osmosignalling and inflammation: how intervertebral disc cells respond to altered osmolarity*. Eur Cell Mater, 2018. **36**: p. 231-250.
5. Tomaszewski, K.A., et al., *Age- and degeneration-related variations in cell density and glycosaminoglycan content in the human cervical intervertebral disc and its endplates*. Pol J Pathol, 2015. **66**(3): p. 296-309.
6. Kibble, M.J., et al., *Importance of Matrix Cues on Intervertebral Disc Development, Degeneration, and Regeneration*. International Journal of Molecular Sciences, 2022. **23**(13): p. 6915.

Figure 1. Effect of the IVD microenvironment on the GAG synthesis rates of NP cells. A) Healthy and degenerate comparison of the IVD nutrient microenvironmental profile. (adapted from [6], created using Biorender.com) B) In silico modelling results of concentrations of oxygen, glucose and pH in media and alginate bead with media changes every 3 days. C) Preliminary data on the effects of osmolarity, pH and glucose variations on GAG synthesis rates. D) Histological staining of glucose on GAG syntheses rates at day 10.